

Carbon Stock Assessment in Peat Soil and Mangrove Regrowth Phase of Shrimp Ponds: A Case Study of Ecosystem Restoration in the Indian Sundarbans

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Abstract

This study investigates Peat Soil Organic Carbon (PSOC) dynamics in abandoned shrimp ponds across two stations in the Indian Sundarbans, Chemaguri (21°39'49.32"N; 88°09'11.88"E) and Sagar Island (South) (21°39'04.68"N; 88°01'47.28"E) selected based on the abundance of shrimp ponds. Shrimp farming, which expanded in the lower Gangetic delta region during the early 1990s, led to extensive loss of mangrove cover and significant reduction in soil carbon storage. In 1994, we recorded the Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) levels of 0.93% and 0.84% in the peat soil during the drying period of shrimp farms (October) at Chemaguri and Sagar Island (South) respectively. Following the introduction of an afforestation program in 2000 aimed at restoring the mangrove ecosystem, significant changes in SOC were observed. By 2014, SOC levels rose to 1.85% and 1.79%, with further increases to 2.45% and 2.01% by 2024, at the respective stations. The study utilized the Walkley-Black method to estimate the SOC levels in the peat soil at different stages like the drying phase of shrimp culture period (1994) and restoration phase (2014 and 2024). This research underscores the positive impact of afforestation programs on mangrove soil recovery and the sequestration of peat soil carbon, confirming the role of mangrove restoration in climate change mitigation and ecosystem rehabilitation

Keywords: Indian Sundarbans, Shrimp farming, Peat Soil Organic Carbon (PSOC).

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1. Introduction

Mangrove ecosystems play a vital role in coastal regions, serving as one of the most efficient carbon sinks due to their high capacity for carbon sequestration, especially in the form of SOC [1-8]. However, the conversion of mangrove forests to aquaculture, particularly shrimp farming, has caused substantial environmental degradation and carbon loss [9-10]. Globally, mangrove deforestation for shrimp aquaculture has led to significant decreases in soil carbon storage, reversing the ecosystem's carbon sink function [11-14].

In the Indian Sundarbans, a UNESCO World Heritage site, shrimp farming expanded significantly in the late 1980s and early 1990s, leading to considerable mangrove loss. By 1994, large tracts of mangroves were cleared for shrimp ponds in the Chemaguri and Sagar Island (South) area of Indian Sundarbans, resulting in reduced SOC levels in affected areas [15]. However, in 2000, an afforestation initiative was introduced to restore abandoned shrimp ponds and rehabilitate mangrove ecosystems. The SOC levels in the region have shown remarkable recovery since the onset of the afforestation program, indicating the restoration potential of these degraded ecosystems.

In shrimp ponds, peat soil undergoes significant changes in terms of soil organic carbon due to poor pond management practices. The organic matter in the soil at depth is often reduced as it gets oxidized under aerobic conditions during the drying phase of the culture pond, leading to lower SOC levels over time. Intensive shrimp farming can also accelerate the depletion of SOC through increased microbial activity and nutrient leaching. Additionally, the accumulation of shrimp feed and waste can alter SOC dynamics through hike in microbial activity, potentially leading to carbon losses in the soil.

This study focuses on two stations in the Indian Sundarbans, Chemaguri and Sagar Island (South). Both areas experienced peak shrimp farming activities in the 1994, followed by mangrove restoration programs initiated in 2000. The SOC levels of the peat soil at these stations were measured at various intervals, namely during October 1994, 2014, and 2024 to assess the impact of restoration efforts on carbon sequestration by the peat soil. Thus, this research aims to understand the relationship between afforestation, mangrove regrowth, and SOC

recovery over time, contributing to broader efforts in ecosystem restoration and climate change mitigation.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The study was conducted at two stations within the Indian Sundarban sector, namely, Chemaguri (21°39'49.32"N; 88°09'11.88"E) and Sagar Island (South) (21°39'04.68"N; 88°01'47.28"E). These areas were historically converted to shrimp ponds in the 1994, contributing to a significant reduction in mangrove cover (Figure 1). Both sites have since undergone restoration under the afforestation program initiated in 2000.

Figure 1: Shrimp ponds in the Indian Sundarbans.

Source: Authors.

2.2 Soil Sampling and Analysis

➤ Sampling

Peat soil samples were collected using a corer from the 50-75 cm depth layer in selected plots (n = 5) at both Chemaguri and Sagar Island (South) stations. The initial sampling took place in October 1994 during the drying phase of shrimp culture ponds, which were later abandoned and planted with mangroves in 2000. Further samples were collected from the same plots in 2014 and 2024 to evaluate the impact of mangrove afforestation on eco-restoration, with Peat Soil Organic Carbon (PSOC) used as an indicator. To ensure precision, three replicate samples were taken from each plot during each sampling period.

➤ Analysis by Walkley-Black Method [16]

A known mass of soil (1 g) was treated with a known excess of 1N potassium dichromate solution. Sulfuric acid was then added, and the mixture was allowed to oxidize for 30 minutes.

The remaining dichromate was titrated with ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using diphenylamine as an indicator. PSOC was calculated as a percentage of the total soil weight based on the amount of dichromate reduced during the reaction, Figure (2).

Figure 2: Analytical flowchart of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) by Walkley-Black Method.

Source: Authors.

For calculation of the percentagem of Carbono (C), have:

$$C = 3.951/g \times (1/B/S)$$

where,

g = weight of sample in grams; B = Mohr salt solution for blank and S = Mohr salt solution for sample.

2.3 Statistical Analysis

PSOC data from the two stations over time (1994, 2014, and 2024) were analyzed to detect significant changes. A two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to assess differences between the stations and across time periods.

3. Results

3.1 PSOC Trends Over Time

In 1994, during the peak shrimp farming period, the PSOC levels were recorded at 0.93% at Chemaguri and 0.84% at Sagar Island (South), reflecting the substantial adverse impact of land-use change and soil disturbance. Both stations experienced a significant increase in PSOC following the initiation of the afforestation program in 2000. By 2014, PSOC values at Chemaguri had risen to 1.85%, while Sagar Island (South) showed an increase to 1.79%. In 2024, the PSOC levels were further elevated to 2.45% at Chemaguri and 2.01% at Sagar Island (South).

These trends indicate a consistent recovery of SOC levels because of mangrove restoration efforts. The increase in PSOC from 1994 to 2024 was significant at both stations, with Chemaguri showing a slightly higher rate of recovery than Sagar Island (South). The results presented in Table (1), analyzed through ANOVA, confirm significant variations across the years ($p < 0.01$) but not between stations.

Table 1: ANOVA showing spatio-temporal variation of SOC.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between years	1.900900	2	0.950450	42.5892	0.0229	19.0000
Between stations	0.058017	1	0.058017	2.5997	0.2482	18.5128
Error	0.044633	2	0.022317	-	-	-
Total	2.00355	5				

Source: Authors. Note: *SS* = Sum of Squares; *df* = Degrees of Freedom; *MS* = Mean Square; *F* = F-ratio; *P-value* = Probability Value; *F crit* = F Critical Value.

3.2 Comparison Between Stations

Figure 3: Variation of SOC (in %) at Chemaguri over a time of 30 years.

Source: Authors.

Figure 4: Variation of SOC (in %) at Sagar Island (South) over a time of 30 years

Source: Authors.

The PSOC recovery rates were slightly different between the two stations. Chemaguri exhibited a higher increase in SOC compared to Sagar Island (South), most likely due to differences in salinity. The relatively low salinity in Chemaguri accelerated the growth of mangroves compared to Sagar Island (South). Sagar Island (South) at the confluence of Bay of Bengal experience high

salinity, which is the basic cause of stunted growth of mangroves [9], [15], [17-20]. The mean SOC increase from 1994 to 2024 was 163.44% at Chemaguri and 139.29% at Sagar Island (South), Figures (3) and (4).

4. Discussions

Shrimp farming, carried out at the cost of mangroves, causes a substantial decline in SOC levels. The removal of mangroves, which are efficient carbon sinks, disrupts their ability to store carbon [21-22]. The conversion of these areas into shrimp ponds enhances carbon release through soil disturbance and oxidation. This ultimately results in a significant loss of SOC and reduces the ecosystem's capacity to sequester carbon, contributing to higher carbon emissions.

Peat soil in shrimp farms, despite being at a greater depth, suffers during the active culture period due to increased oxidation and nutrient leaching caused by pond aeration and water exchange. The disturbance of water flow and sedimentation brings oxygen deeper into the soil, accelerating organic matter breakdown. Additionally, the buildup of shrimp waste and feed can further deplete the soil's organic carbon and nutrients through enhanced microbial activity, leading to soil degradation over time.

The results of this study highlight the success of the afforestation program in enhancing SOC levels in abandoned shrimp ponds. Mangrove regrowth has played a crucial role in the gradual restoration of soil carbon stocks. The increase in SOC over the 30-year period (1994–2024) demonstrates that mangrove ecosystems, when properly managed and restored, have a strong capacity for carbon sequestration, even after extensive degradation. The biomass of mangroves has been observed to be directly proportional to SOC by several researchers [23-26].

The differences in SOC recovery rates between Chemaguri and Sagar Island (South) may be attributed to varying environmental conditions, including soil type, hydrological patterns, and geological features. Chemaguri's relatively higher SOC recovery may be due to more effective tidal flushing, which promotes organic matter deposition and enhanced soil carbon sequestration. Sagar Island (South), on the other hand at the confluence of Bay of Bengal, is an erosion prone zone leading to leaching of surface soil and subsequently SOC. Salinity of the estuarine water also plays a crucial role in the domain of variability of mangrove growth. The relatively low salinity in Chemaguri has promoted faster mangrove growth compared to Sagar Island (South). Sagar Island (South), located at the confluence of the Bay of Bengal, experiences higher salinity levels, which is the primary reason for the stunted growth of mangroves there.

The main species planted in these sites were *Avicennia marina*, *Avicennia alba*, *Avicennia officinalis* and *Sonneratia apetala* (Figures 5 - 8), but the survival rate of *Sonneratia apetala* was relatively low compared to the other species, which might be due to higher degree of salinity in both these stations [9], [17], [24], [27-29] compared to optimum salinity preference of the species for high growth (5-8 PSU).

Figure 5: *Avicennia marina* in the Indian Sundarbans.

Source: Mitra et al. [15].

Restoring mangroves in degraded areas like abandoned shrimp ponds can significantly contribute to climate change mitigation by enhancing carbon sequestration in the peat soil. The recovery of SOC levels in these sites also underscores the importance of integrating coastal ecosystems into national carbon accounting

frameworks. Additionally, the study highlights the value of long-term monitoring and sustainable management practices to maintain soil carbon stocks in mangrove ecosystems.

Figure 6: *Avicennia alba* in the Indian Sundarbans.

Source: Mitra et al. [15].

Figure 7: *Avicennia officinalis* in the Indian Sundarbans.

Source: Mitra et al. [15].

Figure 8: *Sonneratia apetala* in the Indian Sundarbans.

Source: Mitra et al. [15].

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the significant recovery of peat soil organic carbon in abandoned shrimp ponds in the Indian Sundarbans following mangrove restoration efforts. PSOC levels increased from 0.93% and 0.84% in 1994 to 2.45% and 2.01% in 2024 at Chemaguri and Sagar Island (South), respectively. These data imply an increase of 163.44% and 139.29% at Chemaguri and Sagar Island (South), respectively. Our findings underscore the effectiveness of afforestation programs in enhancing carbon sequestration and restoring degraded mangrove ecosystems. Future efforts should focus on sustaining and expanding such initiatives to enhance the resilience of coastal ecosystems and their contribution to climate change mitigation.

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